

Article

Gluability of Thermally Modified Aspen, Birch, and Poplar Rotary Cut Veneers with Suberinic Acids Adhesive

Anete Meija ¹
and Janis Rizikovs ^{3,*}

¹ Institute of Civil Engineering and Woodworking, Latvia University of Life Sciences and Technologies, LV-3001 Jelgava, Latvia; meija.anete@gmail.com (A.M.); uldis.spulle@lbtu.lv (U.S.); luizediena@gmail.com (L.R.)

² National Research Council of Italy, Institute of BioEconomy, 38098 San Michele all'Adige, Italy; ignazia.cuccui@ibe.cnr.it (I.C.); ottaviano.allegretti@ibe.cnr.it (O.A.)

³ Latvian State Institute of Wood Chemistry, LV-1006 Riga, Latvia; aigars.paze@kki.lv

* Correspondence: janis.rizikovs@kki.lv; Tel.: +371-29665012

Abstract: The eco-friendly lifestyle has gained traction at individual and industrial levels, especially following Europe's "Green Deal". While the woodworking industry in Latvia has made strides toward waste-free production, wood processing still produces by-products that require effective utilization. Instead of burning these residues for energy, a sustainable option is repurposing birch bark into suberinic acids adhesive, which is environmentally friendly and safe for humans. Research shows that thermally modified aspen, birch, and poplar veneers treated using the Termovuoto process at 160 °C/50 min, 204 °C/120 min, 214 °C/120 min, 217 °C/180 min, and 218 °C/30 min can be bonded with this adhesive and meet the EN 314-2:1993 standard for outdoor applications classified as Class 3 bonding. However, hydrothermally modified veneers treated at 160 °C 50 min do not bond successfully, failing to meet Class 3 requirements.

Keywords: thermal modification; Termovuoto; hydrothermal treatment; hydrophobic; birch bark; depolymerization; suberinic acids; bio-based adhesive; plywood

Academic Editor: Cinzia Buratti

Received: 28 January 2025

Revised: 20 February 2025

Accepted: 21 February 2025

Published: 26 February 2025

Citation: Meija, A.; Spulle, U.; Ramata, L.; Cuccui, I.; Allegretti, O.; Paze, A.; Rizikovs, J. Gluability of Thermally Modified Aspen, Birch, and Poplar Rotary Cut Veneers with Suberinic Acids Adhesive. *Sustainability* **2025**, *17*, 1990. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su17051990>

Copyright: © 2025 by the authors. Licensee MDPI, Basel, Switzerland. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

1. Introduction

As global demand for wood increases, forests with older trees are offering roundwood with progressively smaller diameters. Consequently, using fast-growing tree species in the wood processing industry is becoming increasingly relevant [1]. However, the wood of fast-growing tree species has certain drawbacks, such as dimensional instability, fibre irregularity, faster biological deterioration, and others. Various wood modification methods can be employed [2–4] to mitigate these disadvantages.

Nowadays, sawn timber and veneers used in plywood production are obtained from small- to medium-diameter roundwood and/or fast-growing tree species. Since veneers are thin materials, they are more susceptible to external biological impacts caused by biotic and abiotic factors, moisture, weather conditions, and direct human influences. Therefore, some preventive actions should be taken to protect this type of wood product, and modification would be one way to do this.

The methods of wood modification can be categorised into active and passive types. Active modification involves chemical changes to the material (e.g., acetylation [5]), whereas passive modification does not entail such alterations (e.g., impregnation [6]). Most methods of active thermal modification involve the reaction of hydroxyl groups in wood-forming

polymers with a reagent. These molecules are responsible for the interaction between wood and water, forming hydrogen bonds with water molecules and contributing to wood swelling and shrinkage. During thermal modification, some of the polymers that constitute the wood cell walls are altered, leading to cross-linking reactions, reduced hydroxyl groups, and undesirable cleavage of polymer chains. This type of modification falls under active modification, as it involves chemical changes within the wood [3].

Thermal modification can improve the properties of veneers and plywood, enhancing their applicability in outdoor conditions and significantly extending their service life [7]. Thermally modified wood has a lower density [8], reduced bending strength [9], stiffness, and wear resistance, leading to a higher tendency to crack. Additionally, its equilibrium moisture content is approximately 40–50% lower than untreated wood at the same relative humidity. Compared with unmodified timber, thermally modified timber exhibits lower thermal conductivity, a higher sound absorption coefficient, reduced fire reaction properties, and a decreased likelihood of insect damage. However, it is not recommended for load-bearing structural applications [10,11].

Wood thermal modification processes can be classified based on the process employed to achieve the desired changes in wood properties [4]. During the thermal modification process, it is crucial to minimise the oxygen availability to prevent its involvement in reactions. Several methods can be employed to achieve this, such as using water steam in the hydrothermal modification process (WTT) [12], utilising an inert gas [13,14], or removing oxygen with a vacuum pump [15].

One of the many well-known thermal modification methods is using vacuum in a Termovuoto (TV) [15] process. This process is conducted in chambers that maintain a consistently low oxygen concentration through a vacuum pump. Compared to alternative thermal modification technologies, the TV process offers higher energy efficiency, reduced mass loss, and lower biodegradability. Additionally, the TV system does not significantly reduce wood's mechanical properties; at temperatures below 190 °C, the decrease in bending strength is not statistically significant [15].

Thermal modification of wood materials used in bonding applications affects adhesive application quality and performance. This modification reduces surface wettability and surface free energy, potentially compromising wood-adhesive bonding by forming a hydrophobic surface layer. Parameters vary depending on the type of adhesives used [16]. In addition, the surface roughness is an important factor that affects the gluability of thermally modified veneers [17].

Beyond gluability, volatile organic compound (VOC) emissions—including free formaldehyde—from wood panels used in furniture and construction products, particularly plywood mobile homes, represent a critical parameter [18]. Plywood manufacturers face the challenge of producing panels with reduced formaldehyde emissions. Consequently, developing environmentally friendly adhesives with minimal VOC emissions has become paramount. Research has been conducted on adhesives incorporating lignin [19], tannins [20], proteins [21], and other sustainable components. There is a lot of research regarding the fully bio-based alternatives to synthetic adhesives, for example, lignin or tannin and their derivatives [22–25]. However, despite the acceptable performance of such adhesives in a dry environment or satisfactory water-resistance test results, the adhesives could not successfully pass the wet shear strength test (boiling water test) related to adhesion performance in a wet environment. Some of them have high viscosity and even poor water resistance, which limits their usability, and therefore, they are improved by additional reagents. Suberinic acids derived from outer birch bark can be a sustainable alternative.

Suberin, a biopolyester composed of α,ω -bifunctional fatty acids, predominantly occurs in plant surface and/or underground tissues, specifically in cell walls of intact and wounded organisms' outer tissues, where it serves as a protective barrier between the organism and its environment [26].

Suberinic acids derived from the depolymerization of birch outer bark have demonstrated strong potential as bio-based adhesives for environmentally friendly wood composites, such as particleboards and plywood [27–30]. These adhesives exhibit excellent water resistance, high bonding strength, and compatibility with wood materials. For particleboards, suberinic acids-based adhesives (SA) achieved mechanical properties comparable to phenol-formaldehyde resins [27,28], meeting European standards for humid environments (EN 312 [31]). Plywood bonded with SA also displayed outstanding durability, conforming to the highest moisture resistance class for unprotected outdoor use [29,30]. Due to the good results, SA offers a sustainable and eco-friendly alternative to synthetic adhesives in wood bonding and related applications. Therefore, the Latvian State Institute of Wood Chemistry has developed and patented a method for obtaining SA from birch outer bark, which can be used for plywood and particleboard production in the hot pressing process [32]. During the hot pressing process, thermosetting SA undergoes curing without additives or modifiers, making it environmentally friendly. Key advantages of SA in plywood production include the following:

- Reduced formaldehyde emissions in furniture manufacturing;
- Healthier environment for sensitive individuals with allergies or respiratory issues;
- Suitability for spaces occupied by children or patients (e.g., hospitals);
- Decreased CO₂ emissions by utilizing birch bark, typically burned for heat;
- New market opportunities for manufacturers emphasizing eco-friendly adhesives.

Although the thermal modification of wood and the use of SA in wood composites have been extensively studied, the bonding of thermally modified veneers with SA has not been investigated to date. Given the environmentally friendly aspects of SA and TV treatment's hydrophobic effects, this study aims to evaluate the quantitative (tensile–shear strength) and qualitative (apparent cohesive wood failure percentage) bonding parameters of aspen, birch, and poplar veneers suitable for plywood production for practical use in Class 3 bonding.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Veneer Thermal Modification

Three wood species were selected for thermal modification: birch (*Betula pendula* Roth. from the Baltic region, average density $599 \pm 43 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$, tensile strength along the fibres $-117 \pm 17 \text{ MPa}$, moisture content (MC) before the modification $-7.9 \pm 0.6\%$), aspen (*Populus tremula* L. from the Baltic region, average density $468 \pm 35 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$, tensile strength along the fibres $-65 \pm 5 \text{ MPa}$, MC before the modification $-7.3 \pm 0.7\%$), and poplar (*Populus x canadensis* Moench. from the Italy region, average density $300 \pm 29 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$, tensile strength along the fibres $-45 \pm 2 \text{ MPa}$, MC before the modification $-7.4 \pm 0.5\%$). Two thermal modification methods were applied: the TV process [15] (see Figure 1a, and the WTT process [12] see Figure 1b).

Veneer thermal modification was performed using five TV treatment conditions and one WTT treatment condition (see Table 1), with the latter representing the most suitable WTT processing parameters previously defined by Grinins et al. [12]. The TV treatment conditions were chosen to replicate the WTT process parameters (TV 160/50), to replicate the mass loss (ML) in WTT 160/50 (TV 214/120), and to have 2% more (TV 217/180) and 2% less (TV 204/120) ML.

Figure 1. Thermal modification of veneers: (a) TV process; (b) WTT process.

Table 1. ML at the different thermal modification conditions.

Modification Conditions	Time (t), min	Temperature (T), °C	Modification Type	ML, %					
				Aspen		Birch		Poplar	
				ML	SD	ML	SD	ML	SD
TV 160/50	50	160	TV	1.24	1.89	1.08	0.24	0	0.69
TV 204/120	120	204	TV	2.94	0.61	2.77	0.46	2.94	0.61
TV 214/120	120	214	TV	4.77	1.28	5.70	0.51	6.50	1.44
TV 217/180	180	217	TV	6.61	0.97	7.77	1.13	8.57	0.76
TV 218/30	30	218	TV	4.24	0.90	4.72	0.57	5.46	0.93
WTT 160/50	50	160	WTT	5.28	1.15	6.66	0.87	5.58	0.74

The process diagram can be seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Thermal modification process diagram [33].

2.2. Mass Loss Determination

The mass loss (ML) of the wood is related to its thermal degradation, and it is considered to be the main indicator of the treatment intensity. The mass of each sample oven-dried

before the treatment (m_0) and after the treatment (m_{ht}) was measured, and the mass loss was determined according to Equation (1):

$$ML = ((m_0 - m_{ht})/m_0) \cdot 100 \quad (1)$$

where m_0 is the untreated dry wood (kg) mass, and m_{ht} is the thermally treated dry wood (kg) mass. ML values for the three species and for the different treatments carried out can be seen in Table 1.

2.3. Density

Density was measured by weighing the 30 samples of each modification and measuring their dimensions before the modification. The density calculation was done according to the standard ISO 13061-2 [34]. After the modification, the calculation of density was done according to Equation (2):

$$\rho_{after} = \rho_{before} \times (m_{after}/m_{before}) \quad (2)$$

2.4. SA Preparation

The production process involves grinding the birch's outer bark and depolymerizing it in a 4% potassium hydroxide aqueous solution. The suspension was heated at 90 °C for 30 min, then cooled to 20 °C. The resulting suberinic acids salt suspension was acidified under stirring to maintain particle suspension, with concentrated nitric acid added until reaching pH 4 ± 1 . The acidified suspension was filtered to separate the suberinic acids and ligno-carbohydrate complex mixture, followed by water washing and filtration to remove coarse particles unsuitable for plywood bonding [32].

2.5. Plywood Bonding

After thermal modification, veneers were conditioned at $65 \pm 5\%$ relative humidity and 20 ± 3 °C. Following moisture content equilibration, the bonding process used thermally modified and unmodified (as reference) aspen, birch, and poplar veneers.

A patented SA [32] was used with the following specifications:

- Fraction size: ≤ 1.0 mm
- Solids content: 20 wt%
- Ash content: 5 wt%
- Acidity: pH 3
- Colour: dark brown

Veneers measuring 290 mm \times 290 mm (length \times width) and 1.5 mm thickness were prepared. For each wood species, two 3-ply plywood panels were assembled. Each veneer sheet was weighed before adhesive application. The SA was applied uniformly using a 10 cm polyacrylic fibre roller to one side of the first two veneers, leaving the top veneer uncoated. Post-application weighing determined adhesive consumption per square meter. The coated veneer sheets were arranged perpendicular to the wood fibre and lightly loaded to prevent moisture-induced curling from uneven swelling and drying. Veneers were dried to a constant mass in a Memmert ULE 500 chamber with internal air circulation at 80 ± 5 °C. After drying, the SA was dark brown (see Figure 3).

Three-layer plywood samples were obtained after pressing the veneers at a temperature of 215 °C and pressure of 1.4 MPa, maintaining the pressure for 5 min. The resulting plywood was conditioned in a climate chamber with a relative humidity of $65 \pm 5\%$ and a temperature of 20 ± 2 °C until a constant mass was achieved. Two plywood samples were made for each modification condition.

Figure 3. Veneer after applying SA adhesive and drying.

It was impossible to bond plywood thermally modified in a hydrothermal process (WTT 160/50) under the current pressing regime, as delamination of the veneers was observed upon removal from the press. This could be attributed to hydrothermal treatment in a water steam environment starting the autocatalytic destruction of wood catalysed by acetic acid formed from hemicelluloses [35]. As a result, the acidic adhesive at the elevated temperature further destroyed the WTT-treated wood and formed reaction water, which inhibited the adhesion to the surface. This means that SA in the conditions used is inappropriate for binding the WTT veneers. To verify the validity of these conclusions, additional studies should be conducted by varying the processing temperature of WTT or the pH of the adhesive. Unfortunately, further testing of these plywood samples was not feasible.

Each plywood sample's thickness was measured before and after pressing, and the compression ratio (CR) was calculated. The CR was determined using the equation (see Equation (3)):

$$CR = ((T_v - T_b)/T_v) \cdot 100 \quad (3)$$

where CR is the compression ratio, in %; T_v is the thickness of the plywood before pressing, in mm; and T_b is the thickness of the plywood after pressing, in mm.

A hydraulic press, "Joos LAP 150", equipped with 600 mm × 600 mm heated pressing plates, was used for plywood bonding. Each three-layer plywood sample was composed of veneers of the same type. When bonding three-layer plywood, two adhesive joints are formed (Figure 4). The adhesive was applied to the first veneer (one of the outer veneers) and the second veneer (the middle layer). The samples were weighed using scales before and after applying the adhesive.

Figure 4. The bonding scheme for three-layer plywood [36]: 1—bottom (outer) veneer; 2—adhesive layer applied to the bottom veneer; 3—middle veneer, with fibre orientation perpendicular to the bottom veneer; 4—second adhesive layer applied to the middle veneer; 5—top (outer) veneer; the red arrow indicates the fibre direction.

2.6. Sample Preparation for Tension-Shear Testing

Samples for evaluating bond strength in tension-shear tests were prepared following the EN-314 standard [37]. Twenty samples were cut from a single 290 mm × 290 mm

three-layer plywood sheet. When cutting the samples, it is critical to ensure that the fibre direction of the outer veneer layers is parallel to the longer edge of the test sample.

According to Part 1 of the EN-314 standard [37], the dimensions of the bond test samples are defined as follows (Figure 5): width: 25 mm; distance between saw-cuts: 25 mm; saw-cut width: 2.5 to 4 mm; saw-cut depth: extending to the midpoint of the middle veneer layer, ensuring symmetry along the test sample's axis of symmetry.

Figure 5. The test specimen [36,37]. The red arrow indicates the fibre direction.

2.7. Pre-Treatment (PT) of Plywood Samples Under Various Conditions Before Testing

Thirty plywood samples were subjected to PT using a Memmert WPE 45 soaking-boiling device under multiple conditions following EN 314 Part 2 [38], which defines bonding classes. Plywood performance indicators were determined using three PT methods:

- 24 h: Immersion in water at 20 ± 3 °C for 24 h.
- 4 h + 16 h + 4 h + 1 h: Immersion in boiling water for 4 h, drying in a ventilated oven at 60 ± 3 °C for 16 h, repeated boiling water immersion for 4 h, followed by cooling in water at 20 ± 3 °C for 1 h.
- 72 h + 1 h: Immersion in boiling water for 72 ± 1 h, followed by cooling in water at 20 ± 3 °C for 1 h.

Ten plywood samples were placed in composite perforated plates and secured with clamps, positioned to avoid contact with one another. The secured plywood samples were subjected to the specified PT methods, adhering to the requirements of Class 3 bonding.

2.8. Testing of Plywood Samples

After PT, the plywood samples were tested using the “ZWICK 10 kN RetroLine” testing machine. The test yielded values for tensile–shear strength (MPa).

Following the failure, the fractured plywood samples were dried to facilitate the evaluation of wood failure (Figure 6). The evaluation criteria for wood failure are detailed in the EN 314-1 [37] standard Annex A. If the fracture within the test square occurs entirely along the adhesive layer, wood failure is 0%. Conversely, if no adhesive layer is visible and the fracture occurs entirely within the wood, it constitutes 100% wood failure. Wood failure is assessed in 5% intervals.

Figure 6. Evaluation of wood failure in test specimens [36]; A—both sides of the test specimen under evaluation; B—test square under evaluation (wood failures).

2.9. Conformity to Class 3 Bonding

According to EN 314-2 [38], after the PT and testing, each glueline shall satisfy two criteria: the mean tensile–shear strength and the mean apparent cohesive wood failure, as combined in the following Table 2:

Table 2. Conformity to Class 3 bonding requirements.

Mean Tensile–Shear Strength f_v , $N \cdot mm^{-2}$	Mean Apparent Cohesive Wood Failure ω , %
$0.2 \leq f_v < 0.4$	≥ 80
$0.4 \leq f_v < 0.6$	≥ 60
$0.6 \leq f_v < 1.0$	≥ 40
$1.0 \leq f_v$	no requirement

2.10. Surface Profile Determination

Surface profile determination was performed using the digital optical microscope HIROX RH-2000. The LED light source provides a 5700 K temperature, which closely portrays daylight colour temperature (5460 K) to re-produce actual sample colour image and full illumination immediately with no warm-up time. The lens used was MXB-2016Z with a field of view (FOV) of 1981 μm at 160 \times magnification and an image resolution of WUXGA 1920 \times 1200 pixels (1.03 μm per pixel). The white balance settings were RGB 171,128,111. The captured 3D profile images (see Figure 7) were mathematically processed, generating surface depth images automatically and displaying the width and length of marked sections in EXCEL (See Figure 8). Surface depth profiles were captured in three parallel planes.

Figure 7. 3D surface depth profile image.

Figure 8. Surface depth profiles.

Subsequently, the depth profile data were mathematically processed, and the surface roughness was determined based on the parameter R_z . The 10-point average roughness R_z was calculated as the mean of the five highest peaks and the five lowest valleys (see Equation (4); Figure 9) [39]:

$$R_z = (|P1 + P2 + P3 + P4 + P5| + |V1 + V2 + V3 + V4 + V5|)/5 \quad (4)$$

Figure 9. Ten-point average roughness calculation [39].

2.11. Data Processing

For each plywood test specimen, tensile–shear strength was determined, and wood failure was assessed for each sample group. For each group of samples, the mean and standard deviation were calculated. Tensile–shear strength reduction compared to unmodified samples ($\Delta\delta$) was calculated by subtracting the unmodified sample tensile–shear strength value in MPa from the modified sample tensile–shear strength value. The treated samples' tensile–shear strength values were compared to unmodified ones using two-sample *t*-tests and evaluating two-tail *p* with the confidence level $\alpha = 0.05$. These values were obtained using the data processing software Microsoft Excel.

3. Results and Discussion

Surface roughness is a property that directly affects the gluability of veneer surfaces, which is critical in plywood production. The surface profile R_z results are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Veneer surface roughness.

Wood Species	Aspen		Birch		Poplar	
	$R_z, \mu\text{m}$	SD (R_z), μm	$R_z, \mu\text{m}$	SD (R_z), μm	$R_z, \mu\text{m}$	SD (R_z), μm
unmodified	56	14	35	7	52	17
WTT 160/50	20	6	8	1	39	17
TV 160/50	28	7	40	14	46	7
TV 204/120	39	10	23	2	106 ¹	36
TV 214/120	36	8	17	1	30	5
TV 217/180	37	6	13	5	39	12
TV 218/30	22	5	14	7	43	19

¹—most likely gross error.

When comparing species, unmodified birch plywood exhibits lower surface roughness than aspen and poplar. According to Bekhta [17], having a veneer with a low surface roughness value is not enough to provide high bonding strength, but it enhances it. Compared to the surface roughness parameters obtained by Rohumaa [40]— $88 \pm 14 \mu\text{m}$ for unmodified birch veneers and $140 \pm 38 \mu\text{m}$ for unmodified aspen veneers—the surface roughness parameter for veneers used for this research is twice less, which can be explained by the different methods used to obtain the result.

Thermal birch veneer modification reduces surface roughness in all regimes except TV 160/50, with considerable variance observed in roughness measurements. Thermal modification of aspen decreases surface roughness across all regimes, with the smoothest surface achieved under the most severe conditions—WTT 160/50 and TV 218/30. The TV 217/180 modification produces more pronounced surface roughness, indicating that temperature impacts this parameter more than treatment duration. Similarly, all thermal modifications reduce surface roughness in poplar, compared to unmodified ones. The anomalous result observed in the TV 204/120 modified sample likely stems from poor specimen selection or gross experimental error. Increased surface roughness decreases the contact angle on hydrophilic surfaces, enhancing water absorption capacity [41].

The SA consumption varies for each thermal modification condition of veneers (see Table 4).

Table 4. SA consumption and CR mean values.

Wood Species	Aspen				Birch				Poplar			
	Modification Conditions	CR, %	SD	SA Dry Matter Consumption, $\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$	SD	CR, %	SD	SA Dry Matter Consumption, $\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$	SD	CR, %	SD	SA Dry Matter Consumption, $\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$
unmodified	9.4	0.1	95	0.1	15.0	0.2	93	0.2	11.4	0.1	95	0.3
WTT 160/50	9.4	0.2	85	0.3	14.8	1.0	85	0.3	11.5	0.2	86	0.4
TV 160/50	9.4	0.1	92	0.2	14.8	0.2	90	0.4	11.1	0.2	93	0.2
TV 204/120	9.5	0.3	90	0.9	15.3	0.1	89	0.1	10.7	0.6	91	0.2
TV 214/120	9.6	0.5	88	1.8	15.3	0.9	88	0.1	11.1	0.4	90	0.1
TV 217/180	9.2	0.2	86	0.8	14.6	0.3	86	0.2	11.4	0.2	87	0.3
TV 218/30	9.3	0.0	88	0.4	14.7	0.5	85	0.3	11.6	0.4	89	0.4

A trend can be observed in the consumption of SA, which decreases as the thermal modification temperature and duration increase. This trend is associated with the hydrophobicity of the surface of thermally modified veneers. However, the adhesive dry matter consumption among all thermal modification conditions does not significantly differ, with average values of $89 \pm 3 \text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$ for aspen, $88 \pm 3 \text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$ for birch, and $90 \pm 3 \text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$ for poplar. The highest compression was achieved for birch plywood, with CRs of $15.3 \pm 0.1\%$ for TV 204/120 and $15.3 \pm 0.9\%$ for TV 214/120. The previous research has revealed that the CR depends on the density, and for the unmodified birch plywood, it can vary from 12% for the highest density ($644\text{--}690 \text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) of birch veneers to 18% for the lowest density ($502\text{--}540 \text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) group of birch veneers [42]. The lowest CR in this research, $9.2 \pm 0.2\%$, was observed for aspen TV 217/180 plywood, while the lowest CR for poplar plywood was $10.7 \pm 0.6\%$ TV 204/120 (see Table 4). The CR of unmodified aspen ($9.4 \pm 0.1\%$) plywood is lower than that of unmodified birch ($15 \pm 0.2\%$), contrary to the findings of Kallakas et al. [43], who declared that the CR of seven-ply plywood consisting of five inner aspen plies is higher compared to seven-ply birch plywood.

Density results were previously published for aspen, poplar, and birch specimens. Figure 10 below shows the correlation between CR and density. It clearly shows that CR depends more on wood species, timber age, and growth conditions than just density, which contradicts previous conclusions [42].

Figure 10. CR as a function of density for each species.

After the bonding of the plywood and sample preparation according to the dimensions shown in Figure 5, the samples were conditioned in all three PT environments before tensile–shear testing following the EN 314 standard [38] to assess the potential compliance of the resulting plywood with the Class 3 bonding or suitability for outdoor use.

When conditioned for 24 h in water at $20 \pm 3 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, unmodified birch plywood showed a tensile–shear strength value of $1.80 \pm 0.13 \text{ MPa}$; after PT 4 h + 16 h + 4 h + 1 h, the corresponding value was $1.10 \pm 0.06 \text{ MPa}$, and after the harshest PT 72 h + 1 h, it was $0.90 \pm 0.05 \text{ MPa}$. The strength reduction $\Delta\delta$ depending on mass loss after all PT of birch samples can be seen in Figure 11. A trend was observed where the plywood’s tensile–shear strength decreased as the veneer ML increased. A *t*-test showed that the modified tensile–shear strength reduction for all birch plywood samples is statistically significant compared to unmodified samples ($p < 0.05$), except for birch plywood TV 160/50 after 72 h + 1 h PT, where $p = 0.59$.

Figure 11. Birch plywood $\Delta\delta$ depending on ML after three sets of PT.

After PT for 24 h, unmodified aspen plywood showed a tensile–shear strength value of $1.47 \pm 0.17 \text{ MPa}$; after PT 4 h + 16 h + 4 h + 1 h, the corresponding value was $0.93 \pm 0.04 \text{ MPa}$, and after PT 72 h + 1 h, it was $0.77 \pm 0.20 \text{ MPa}$. The strength reduction $\Delta\delta$ depending on mass loss after all sets of PT of aspen samples can be seen in Figure 12. The same trend was observed for birch plywood, where, as the ML of veneers increased, the tensile–shear strength of the plywood decreased, with the slight exception in modification condition TV 217/180. A *t*-test showed that the modified tensile–shear strength reduction

for all aspen plywood samples is statistically significant compared to unmodified samples ($p < 0.05$), except for aspen plywood TV 160/50 after 72 h + 1 h PT, where $p = 0.22$.

Figure 12. Aspen plywood $\Delta\delta$ depending on ML after three sets of PT.

After PT for 24 h, unmodified poplar plywood showed a tensile–shear strength value of 1.24 ± 0.10 MPa; after PT 4 h + 16 h + 4 h + 1 h, the corresponding value was 0.84 ± 0.03 MPa, and after PT 72 h + 1 h, it was 0.65 ± 0.04 MPa. The strength reduction $\Delta\delta$ depending on mass loss after all sets of PT of poplar samples can be seen in Figure 13. The same trend was observed for birch and aspen plywood, where, as the ML of veneers increased, the tensile–shear strength of the plywood decreased, except for the regimes TV 204/120 and TV 214/120. A t -test showed that the modified tensile–shear strength difference for all poplar plywood samples is statistically significant compared to unmodified samples ($p < 0.05$). As all the measured and calculated mean tensile–shear strength values, except for unmodified poplar plywood after PT 24 h, were below 1 MPa, it was essential to determine the average apparent cohesive wood failure (see Table 5).

The following qualitative values are necessary to determine the compliance of the tested aspen, birch, and poplar plywood with Class 3 bonding, as specified by the requirements of standard EN 314-2 [38]. According to this standard, the lower the tensile–shear strength (below the threshold of 1 MPa), the higher the wood failure percentage shall be [38].

Figure 13. Poplar plywood $\Delta\delta$ depending on ML after three sets of PT.

Table 5. The average apparent cohesive wood failure percentage.

Modification Conditions	The Average Apparent Cohesive Wood Failure, %								
	Aspen			Birch			Poplar		
	24 h	4 h + 16 h + 4 h + 1 h	72 h + 1 h ¹	24 h	4 h + 16 h + 4 h + 1 h	72 h + 1 h ¹	24 h	4 h + 16 h + 4 h + 1 h	72 h + 1 h
unmodified	100	70	65	100	70	65	100	70	65
TV 160/50	50	70	65	75	60	60	95	70	65
TV 204/120	55	60	65	80	70	65	100	65	75
TV 214/120	70	60	75	80	60	75	100	60	75
TV 217/180	90	60	65	80	50	65	70	60	80
TV 218/30	70	60	65	80	55	75	60	80	75

¹ See Figure 14.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 14. Plywood specimens after 72 h + 1 h pre-treatment and testing: (a) aspen TV 217/180; (b) birch TV 217/180; (c) poplar TV 160/50.

All obtained results show that both plywood from unmodified veneers and plywood from thermally modified veneers under the conditions TV 160/50, TV 204/120, TV 214/120, TV 217/180, and TV 218/30 comply with Class 3 bonding, according to the requirements of the EN 314-2 standard [38].

Aspen and poplar could be future wood resources utilized in plywood production, as they can achieve the desired material strength and cohesive failure. In a study conducted by Akkurt and other authors [44] on producing nine-ply plywood from common aspen (2.6 mm thick), it was concluded that the final product's mass, production costs, and mechanical properties (−24% MOR in grain direction compared to unmodified birch plywood and −17% MOR in cross direction compared to unmodified birch plywood) decreased, which is comparable with this research's results (−18% tensile–shear strength PT 24 h; −15% PT 4 h + 16 h + 4 h + 1 h; −14% PT 72 h + 1 h).

These aspects should be considered when selecting the appropriate wood species for plywood production and evaluating the potential uses of the final product. The same factors must be considered when using aspen and poplar for plywood production, especially since the thermal modification process leads to additional mass loss of the veneers [15]. Given that the contribution of SA to the mass of the investigated plywood is significant—up to 20% of the dry mass—using aspen and poplar veneers, which are considerably lighter and less dense compared to birch veneers, could provide a tremendous advantage. If we consider density the primary indicator for a higher-strength final product, one of the ways to increase plywood production efficiency or reduce adhesive consumption, pressing pressure, and time is to pre-compress the veneers before the glueing process. Pressing birch veneers at a pressure of 2 MPa for 1 min leads to compression, and using compressed veneers can reduce hot pressing time by 17 to 50%, adhesive consumption by 33.3% (when using phenol-formaldehyde resin), and pressing pressure by 22.2%, without reducing the mechanical properties and quality of the plywood [45]. This can be useful for further studies, optimizing the plywood manufacturing process. Pre-pressing could be applied to aspen and poplar wood for the studied tree species.

Birch veneers were thermally modified at 180 °C and 220 °C for 180 min and then glued with hot-curing liquid phenol-formaldehyde resin. The bonding strength for 10 min of open assembly, and the 160 s pressing time decreased by 10% and 36%, respectively, compared to unmodified birch samples [46]. For TV 217/180, the decrease was 41% PT 24 h, 48% PT 4 h + 16 h + 4 h + 1 h, and 40% PT 72 h + 1 h. The difference can be explained by the fact that no PT was in the previously mentioned study. Although the mass loss during thermal modification in the open process is higher than in the TV process, the PT decreases the bonding strength. Another research reveals that at 200 °C in steam conditions, for 120 min, 240 min, and 480 min, thermally modified birch veneers were glued using phenol-formaldehyde (PF) resin. After 180 s of pressing (130 °C and 2.0 MPa), the shear strength of the adhesive bond was measured, and it was only slightly reduced compared to untreated samples [47], in contradiction to WTT 160/50 glued with SA, which was delaminating.

Plywood can be manufactured from hardwoods and softwoods, according to the research of Galdino et al. [48], which is focused on 2.3 mm thick *Pinus taeda* veneers thermally modified in a hot press at 1 MPa at 160 °C, 180 °C, and 200 °C for 30 min and glued (90 °C, 0.6 MPa, and 10 min) with castor oil-based polyurethane adhesive. The tensile–shear strength results for all treatment regimes were above 1 MPa, and it was concluded that heating above 160 °C for 30 min is sufficient for changes in the veneer, such as to soften the wood material and reduce its roughness, which coincides with the results obtained in this study.

The thermal modification of poplar plywood has also been studied [49]. Plywood was bonded using veneers of unmodified poplar (*Populus* spp.) and melamine–urea–formaldehyde resin adhesive. Following assembly, the poplar plywood was thermally modified in a TV environment for 2 h at three different temperatures: 170 °C, 190 °C, and 210 °C. According to the EN 314 standard [38], all test samples met the requirements for Class 2 bonding (use in humid outdoor conditions). The most suitable thermal modification conditions for poplar plywood in a TV environment are at 190 °C for 2 h. Plywood treated under these conditions would be ideal for camper furniture, covered outdoor environments, external cladding, partitions, and outdoor flooring [50]. Similar trends have been observed in other studies involving various wood species and adhesives [51].

Based on the findings discussed above, it can be concluded that the thermal modification of aspen, birch, and poplar veneers in a TV process combined with the use of SA under the parameters of 215 °C temperature, 1.4 MPa pressure, and 5 min of pressing time meets the requirements of standard EN 314 [38]. Therefore, they are suitable for environmental conditions classified as Class 3 bonding and for producing plywood as cladding elements for external building facades. However, veneers modified in the hydrothermal process under the WTT 160/50 regime could not be glued under the same bonding conditions.

The preliminary study conducted in this research can serve as a foundation for future investigations to optimise the technological parameters of SA bonding, including variations in pressing temperature, pressure, and duration. The long-term durability of SA adhesive could also be evaluated.

4. Conclusions

1. Unmodified birch plywood exhibits lower surface roughness ($35 \pm 7 \mu\text{m}$) than unmodified aspen ($56 \pm 14 \mu\text{m}$) and poplar ($52 \pm 17 \mu\text{m}$). Thermal modification of birch reduces surface roughness in all regimes except TV 160/50 ($40 \pm 14 \mu\text{m}$); thermal modification of aspen and poplar decreases surface roughness across all modification conditions compared to unmodified ones.
2. Veneers thermally modified in the TV process under all selected modification conditions successfully bonded with the SA under the chosen bonding conditions (press plate temperature of 215 °C, pressing pressure of 1.4 MPa, and pressing time of 5 min). However, veneers modified in the hydrothermal process under the WTT 160/50 regime could not be glued under the same bonding conditions.
3. Unmodified plywood exhibited higher SA consumption, ranging from 93 (birch) to 95 $\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$ (aspen and poplar). In contrast, birch plywood modified under the TV 218/30 regime demonstrated a 9% lower SA consumption, likely due to the modified veneers' hydrophobicity and potentially reduced surface roughness.
4. Birch plywood exhibited the highest CR, at 15.3%, in TV 204/120 and TV 214/120 conditions. In comparison, aspen plywood had a CR of 37.3% lower at TV 214/120, while poplar plywood had a CR of 30% lower at TV 204/120. CR is not dependent on density only, as was believed before.
5. Aspen, birch, and poplar veneers, as well as veneers modified in the TV process under all tested conditions and bonded with SA under the parameters of 215 °C temperature, 1.4 MPa pressure, and 5 min of pressing time, meet the requirements of standard EN 314 [38]. Therefore, they are suitable for use in environmental conditions classified as Class 3 bonding.
6. After PT for 72 h + 1 h, unmodified birch plywood reveals the highest tensile–shear strength values ($0.90 \pm 0.05 \text{ MPa}$), followed by TV 160/50 ($0.87 \pm 0.16 \text{ MPa}$), TV 204/120 ($0.76 \pm 0.07 \text{ MPa}$), TV 218/30 ($0.66 \pm 0.09 \text{ MPa}$), TV 214/120 ($0.65 \pm 0.14 \text{ MPa}$), and TV 217.180 ($0.54 \pm 0.04 \text{ MPa}$).

Author Contributions: Conceptualisation, A.M. and U.S.; methodology, I.C., O.A., A.P. and J.R.; investigation, L.R. and A.M.; resources, U.S., I.C., O.A. and J.R.; writing—original draft preparation, A.M. and U.S.; writing—review and editing, J.R., I.C., O.A. and A.P.; visualisation, A.M. and L.R.; supervision, U.S.; project administration, J.R.; funding acquisition, U.S. and J.R. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research was conducted within the Latvian State research program project No. VPP-ZM-VRIILA-2024/2-0002 “Innovation in Forest Management and Value Chain for Latvia’s Growth: New Forest Services, Products and Technologies (Forest4LV)”.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: The dataset is available upon request from the authors.

Acknowledgments: Special thanks to Haralds Šillers for the visualisation of test specimen data.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflicts of interest. The funders had no role in the design of the study, in the collection, analysis, or interpretation of data, in the writing of the manuscript, or in the decision to publish the results.

Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

TV	Termovuoto—wood thermal modification process in lowered pressure
WTT	Wood treatment technology—wood hydrothermal modification process in a water steam environment
VOC	Volatile organic compounds
SA	Suberinic acids-based adhesive
CR	Compression ratio
SD	Standard deviation
ML	Mass loss
$\Delta\delta$	Tensile–shear strength reduction compared to unmodified samples
PT	Pre-treatment
MC	Moisture content

References

- Elorriaga, E.; Klocko, A.L.; Ma, C.; Strauss, S.H. Variation in mutation spectra among CRISPR/Cas9 mutagenized poplars. *Front. Plant Sci.* **2018**, *9*, 594. [[CrossRef](#)]
- Wang, X.; Tu, D.; Chen, C.; Zhou, Q.; Huang, H.; Zheng, Z.; Zhu, Z. A thermal modification technique combining bulk densification and heat treatment for poplar wood with low moisture content. *Constr. Build. Mater.* **2021**, *291*, 123395. [[CrossRef](#)]
- Sandberg, D.; Kutnar, A.; Mantanis, G. Wood modification technologies—A review. *IForest* **2017**, *10*, 895–908. [[CrossRef](#)]
- Jones, D.; Sandberg, D.; Goli, G.; Todaro, L. *Wood modification in Europe: A State-of-the-Art About Processes, Products and Applications*, 1st ed.; Firenze University Press: Firenze, Italy, 2020; ISBN 978-88-6453-970-6.
- Wang, Y.; Wang, T.; Crocetti, R.; Wälinder, M. Experimental investigation on mechanical properties of acetylated birch plywood and its angle-dependence. *Constr. Build. Mater.* **2022**, *344*, 128277. [[CrossRef](#)]
- Căpraru, A.M.; Ungureanu, E.; Popa, V.I. Studies on the interaction between birch veneer and compounds with biocide potential action. *Environ. Eng. Manag. J.* **2008**, *7*, 525–530. [[CrossRef](#)]

7. Hsu, F.Y.; Hung, K.C.; Xu, J.W.; Liu, J.W.; Wu, Y.H.; Chang, W.S.; Wu, J.H. Analyzing the impact of veneer layup direction and heat treatment on plywood strain distribution during bending load by digital image correlation (DIC) technique. *J. Mater. Res. Technol.* **2023**, *27*, 5257–5265. [[CrossRef](#)]
8. Barčík, Š.; Gašparík, M.; Razumov, E.Y. Effect of temperature on the color changes of wood during thermal modification. *Cellul. Chem. Technol.* **2015**, *49*, 789–798.
9. Castro, G.; Rosso, L.; Allegretti, O.; Cuccui, I.; Cremonini, C.; Negro, F.; Zanuttini, R. Influence of thermo-vacuum treatment on bending properties of poplar rotary-cut veneer. *IForest* **2017**, *10*, 161–163. [[CrossRef](#)]
10. Borůvka, V.; Dudík, R.; Zeidler, A.; Holeček, T. Influence of site conditions and quality of birch wood on its properties and utilization after heat treatment. Part I—elastic and strength properties, relationship to water and dimensional stability. *Forests* **2019**, *10*, 189. [[CrossRef](#)]
11. Boruvka, V.; Zeidler, A.; Holeček, T.; Dudík, R. Elastic and strength properties of heat-treated beech and birch wood. *Forests* **2018**, *9*, 197. [[CrossRef](#)]
12. Grīniņš, J. Bērza Saplākšņa Īpašību Uzlabošana Ar Hidrotermiskās Modifikācijas Paņēmienu—in Latvian. (Improvement of Birch Plywood Properties Using the Hydrothermal Modification Method). Ph.D. Thesis, Riga Technical University, Riga, Latvia, 2016.
13. Bytner, O.; Drożdżek, M.; Laskowska, A.; Zawadzki, J. Influence of Thermal Modification in Nitrogen Atmosphere on the Selected Mechanical Properties of Black Poplar Wood (*Populus nigra* L.). *Materials* **2022**, *15*, 7949. [[CrossRef](#)]
14. Sosins, G.; Grinins, J.; Brazdauskis, P.; Zicans, J. Aspen Wood Characteristics Following Thermal Modification in Closed Process Under Pressure in Nitrogen. *Materials* **2024**, *17*, 5930. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
15. Sandak, A.; Allegretti, O.; Cuccui, I.; Sandak, J.; Rosso, L.; Castro, G.; Negro, F.; Cremonini, C.; Zanuttini, R. Thermo-vacuum modification of poplar veneers and its quality control. *BioResources* **2016**, *11*, 10122–10139. [[CrossRef](#)]
16. Masoumi, A.; Balma, F.X.Z.; Bond, B.H. Adhesive bonding performance of thermally modified yellow poplar. *BioResources* **2023**, *18*, 8151–8162. [[CrossRef](#)]
17. Bekhta, P.; Niemz, P.; Sedliacik, J. Effect of pre-pressing of veneer on the glueability and properties of veneer-based products. *Eur. J. Wood Wood Prod.* **2012**, *70*, 99–106. [[CrossRef](#)]
18. Böhm, M.; Salem, M.Z.M.; Srba, J. Formaldehyde emission monitoring from a variety of solid wood, plywood, blockboard and flooring products manufactured for building and furnishing materials. *J. Hazard. Mater.* **2012**, *221–222*, 68–79. [[CrossRef](#)]
19. Yang, G.; Gong, Z.; Luo, X.; Chen, L.; Shuai, L. Bonding wood with uncondensed lignins as adhesives. *Nature* **2023**, *621*, 511–515. [[CrossRef](#)]
20. Li, C.; Zhang, J.; Yi, Z.; Yang, H.; Zhao, B.; Zhang, W.; Li, J. Preparation and characterization of a novel environmentally friendly phenol-formaldehyde adhesive modified with tannin and urea. *Int. J. Adhes. Adhes.* **2016**, *66*, 26–32. [[CrossRef](#)]
21. Yue, H.; Mai, L.; Xu, C.; Yang, C.; Shuttleworth, P.S.; Cui, Y. Recent advancement in bio-based adhesives derived from plant proteins for plywood application: A review. *Sustain. Chem. Pharm.* **2023**, *33*, 101143. [[CrossRef](#)]
22. Oktay, S.; Pizzi, A.; Köken, N.; Bengü, B. Tannin-based wood panel adhesives. *Int. J. Adhes. Adhes.* **2024**, *130*, 103621. [[CrossRef](#)]
23. Peng, J.; Lei, J.; Feng, F.; Liu, F.; Ma, Y.; Bai, J.; Da, G.; Wei, C.; Huo, Z.; Cui, J. Eco-friendly and novel tannin-based wood adhesive enhanced with cellulose nanofibrils grafted by hyperbranched polyamides. *Ind. Crops Prod.* **2024**, *222*, 119576. [[CrossRef](#)]
24. Siahkamari, M.; Emmanuel, S.; Hodge, D.B.; Nejad, M. Lignin-glyoxal: A fully biobased formaldehyde-free wood adhesive for interior engineered wood products. *ACS Sustain. Chem. Eng.* **2022**, *10*, 10701–10711. [[CrossRef](#)]
25. Yuan, J.; Du, G.; Yang, H.; Liu, S.; Park, S.; Liu, T.; Ran, X.; Park, B.D.; Gao, W.; Yang, L. Fully bio-based adhesive designed through lignin-cellulose combination and interfacial bonding reinforcement. *Ind. Crops Prod.* **2023**, *204*, 117279. [[CrossRef](#)]
26. Gandini, A.; Neto, C.P.; Silvestre, A.J.D. Suberin: A promising renewable resource for novel macromolecular materials. *Prog. Polym. Sci.* **2006**, *31*, 878–892. [[CrossRef](#)]
27. Tupciauskas, R.; Rizhikovs, J.; Grinins, J.; Paze, A.; Andzs, M.; Brazdauskis, P.; Puke, M.; Plavniece, A. Investigation of suberinic acids-bonded particleboard. *Eur. Polym. J.* **2019**, *113*, 176–182. [[CrossRef](#)]
28. Rizhikovs, J.; Brazdauskis, P.; Paze, A.; Tupciauskas, R.; Grinins, J.; Puke, M.; Plavniece, A.; Andzs, M.; Godina, D.; Makars, R. Characterization of suberinic acids from birch outer bark as bio-based adhesive in wood composites. *Int. J. Adhes. Adhes.* **2022**, *112*, 102989. [[CrossRef](#)]
29. Paze, A.; Rizhikovs, J. Study of an appropriate suberinic acids binder for gluing of plywood. *Key Eng. Mater.* **2019**, *800*, 251–257. [[CrossRef](#)]
30. Paze, A.; Rizhikovs, J.; Godina, D.; Makars, R.; Berzins, R. Development of plywood binder by partial replacement of phenol-formaldehyde resins with birch outer bark components. *Key Eng. Mater.* **2021**, *903*, 229–236. [[CrossRef](#)]
31. EN 312:2010; Particleboards—Specifications. European Committee for Standardization: Brussels, Belgium, 2010.
32. Rižikovs, J.; Pāže, A.; Makars, R.; Tupčiauskas, R. A Method for Obtaining Thermoreactive Binders for a Production of Wood Composite Materials from Birch Outer Bark. WO2021/024152A1, 11 February 2021.
33. Biziks, V.; Andersons, B.; Sansonetti, E.; Andersone, I.; Militz, H.; Grinins, J. One-stage thermo-hydro treatment (THT) of hardwoods: An analysis of form stability after five soaking–drying cycles. *Holzforschung* **2015**, *69*, 563–571. [[CrossRef](#)]

34. ISO 13061-2; Physical and Mechanical Properties of Wood—Test Methods for Small Clear Wood Specimens—Part 2: Determination of Density for Physical and Mechanical Tests. International Organization for Standardization: Geneva, Switzerland, 2014.
35. Tjeerdsma, B.F.; Militz, H. Chemical changes in hydrothermal treated wood: FTIR analysis of combined hydrothermal and dry heat-treated wood. *Holz als Roh- und Werkst.* **2005**, *63*, 102–111. [[CrossRef](#)]
36. Šillers, H. Termiski modificētu apses, bērza un papeles finieru līmēšana.—in Latvian (Bonding of Thermally Modified Aspen, Birch, and Poplar Veneers). Master’s Thesis, Latvia University of Biosciences and Technology, Jelgava, Latvia, 2022.
37. EN 314-1:2004; Plywood—Bonding Quality—Part 1: Test Methods. European Committee for Standardization: Brussels, Belgium, 2004.
38. EN 314-2:1993; Plywood—Bonding Quality—Part 2: Requirements. European Committee for Standardization: Brussels, Belgium, 1993.
39. Zein, H. Investigation of surface texture and surface residual stresses in the dry face turning process of AL2024-T351. *Int. J. Mech. Mechatron. Eng.* **2020**, *20*, 123–143.
40. Rohumaa, A.; Kallakas, H.; Mäetalu, M.; Savest, N.; Kers, J. The effect of surface properties on bond strength of birch, black alder, grey alder and aspen veneers. *Int. J. Adhes. Adhes.* **2021**, *110*, 102945. [[CrossRef](#)]
41. Keržič, E.; Lesar, B.; Humar, M. Influence of weathering on surface roughness of thermally modified wood. *BioRes* **2021**, *16*, 4675–4692. [[CrossRef](#)]
42. Kūliņš, L.; Meija, A.; Roziņš, R.; Liepa, K.H.; Spulle, U. Influence of veneer density on plywood thickness and some mechanical properties. *Rural. Sustain. Res.* **2021**, *46*, 66–74. [[CrossRef](#)]
43. Kallakas, H.; Rohumaa, A.; Vahermets, H.; Kers, J. Effect of different hardwood species and lay-up schemes on the mechanical properties of plywood. *Forests* **2020**, *11*, 649. [[CrossRef](#)]
44. Akkurt, T.; Kallakas, H.; Rohumaa, A.; Hunt, C.G.; Kers, J. Impact of aspen and black alder substitution in birch plywood. *Forests* **2022**, *13*, 142. [[CrossRef](#)]
45. Bekhta, P.; Sedliačik, J.; Bekhta, N. Effects of selected parameters on the bonding quality and temperature evolution inside plywood during pressing. *Polymers* **2020**, *12*, 1035. [[CrossRef](#)]
46. Bastani, A.; Militz, H.; Adamopoulos, S.; Rohumaa, A. Development of bonding strength of modified birch veneers during adhesive curing. *Wood Res.* **2016**, *61*, 205–213.
47. Lillqvist, K.; Rohumaa, A.; Källbom, S.; Rautkari, L.; Wälinder, M. The influence of thermal modification on veneer bond strength. In Proceedings of the 13th Annual Meeting of the Northern European Network for Wood Science and Engineering, Copenhagen, Denmark, 28–29 September 2017.
48. Galdino, D.S.; Silva, M.F.F.; Arroyo, F.N.; Rangel, E.C.; Caraschi, J.C.; Santos, H.F.; Freitas, L.; Christoforo, A.L.; Campos, C.I. Properties of plywood made of thermally treated veneers bonded with castor oil-based polyurethane adhesive. *Forests* **2023**, *14*, 1635. [[CrossRef](#)]
49. Zanuttini, R.; Castro, G.; Cremonini, C.; Negro, F.; Palanti, S. Thermo-vacuum treatment of poplar (*Populus* spp.) plywood. *Holzforschung* **2020**, *74*, 60–67. [[CrossRef](#)]
50. Zanuttini, R.; Negro, F.; Cremonini, C. Hardness and contact angle of thermo-treated poplar plywood for bio-building. *IForest* **2021**, *14*, 274–277. [[CrossRef](#)]
51. Krystofiak, T.; Lis, B.; Muszyńska, M.; Karolina, S. Gluability of thermally modified ash wood with EPI adhesives. In Proceedings of the Characterization of Modified Wood in Relation to Wood Bonding and Coating Performance, Rogla, Slovenia, 16–18 October 2013. [[CrossRef](#)]

Disclaimer/Publisher’s Note: The statements, opinions and data contained in all publications are solely those of the individual author(s) and contributor(s) and not of MDPI and/or the editor(s). MDPI and/or the editor(s) disclaim responsibility for any injury to people or property resulting from any ideas, methods, instructions or products referred to in the content.